

Multi-cubic Trees in the Subset Sum Problem

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ABSTRACT

It's known that the subset sum problem lies in the NP-class of complexity, however, due to the integer factorization of any number it states another argument towards $P = NP$.

DESCRIPTION

The "P versus NP" problem is the main problem stated before [1].

We simply factorize numbers within the prime number factorization algorithm and build on-level tree structure for finding the structure of the method.

As we know the prime factorization is reminiscent of the tractable logic of computer numbers which tend to limit the Ackermann numbers [2].

The prime factorization itself isn't studied nowadays and is well-known [3] to be P-complete within the subquadratic algorithm which is still inefficient against big numbers which are met in cryptography [4].

Still it's omitted that the subset sum problem can be devised from the whole set of problems within the multi-cubic trees along prime factorization and prime number notation system [5].

Still it's posed that linear complexity of introduced parameters harms the overall magnitude of complexity, which is well-known and can be factored according to the optimal notation of consecutive prime numbers to which the parameter tends to grow linearly with predefined maximal speed of Ackermann numbers.

We build the growing structure of the tree on each level having the prime number in prime notation of the parameter whose limit is to be deduced from even factorial decomposition which leads to blow and speed-up and, thus, makes the free parameter less playing the role.

CONCLUSION

The overall can be considered as the other argument towards "P versus NP" theorem and the proof $P = NP$, as the subset sum is both in P and NP and NP-complete classes of complexity.

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